

Factors That Influence the Turnover Intentions of Employees in the Tourism Sector in Zimbabwe

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Abstract:

This study was aimed at identifying the major factors that influence the turnover intentions of employees in the tourism sector in Zimbabwe. The Zimbabwean tourism sector has been losing professional guides and hunters to competitors operating in the neighbouring countries such as Botswana, Namibia and South Africa. The regression results suggest that gender, education, push and pull factors significantly influence turnover intentions of employees in the tourism sector. Therefore, human resource managers in the Zimbabwean tourism sector need to pay more attention to these factors in order to minimise the employee turnover rate

Keywords; *intention to quit, employee turnover, turnover intentions, Zimbabwean tourism sector*

1. INTRODUCTION

A considerable amount of literature has been published on voluntary employee turnover (hereafter, employee turnover). To the organization; employee turnover implies loss of talented and well experienced professionals, inevitably leading to high costs in the recruitment and training of new staff (Loi, *et al*, 2006). Thus, the problem of employee turnover significantly affects the performance, productivity and profitability of organisations (Mohamed and Mohamed, 2013). A great deal of research has mainly focused on explaining why employees quit their jobs and it has imaged that the majors factors that influence employee turnover can be grouped as personal factors, organizational and work factors and social and economic factors (Zhang, 2016). In addition, Price (2000), Loi, *et al*,(2006) and Castle (2007) have argued that employee turnover is highly correlated with intention to quit a job and as a result, the recent studies have focused more on turnover intentions (Tham, 2007; Peterson, 2009; Ghazali, 2010; Martin, 2011; Medina, 2012; Rosenkranz, 2012; Almalki *et al*, 2012 and Nyamubarwa, 2013). Thus identifying the major determinants of employee turnover intention can help the human resources managers to accurately predict turnover behaviours and therefore take necessary measures to possibly minimise the employee turnover rate (Hwang and Kuo, 2006; Schalkwyk, *et al*, 2010; Omar *et al*, 2012). The present study, therefore, focuses on factors that influence the turnover intentions of employees in the tourism sector in Zimbabwe

The Tourism industry in Zimbabwe is comprised of the various sub sectors such as; Hotels and Lodges, Safari Operators, Travel and Tour Operators and Conservation and Natural resource Preservation. Zimbabwe Tourism sector currently employs approximately 300 000 people in aggregate both directly and indirectly (ZTA, 2012), 28% of which are women. Eleven percent of these women are in leadership positions (Ministry of Tourism and Hospitality Industry's 2009 estimates). This accounts for 2.2- 3 % of formally employed people in Zimbabwe.

The Employer Association for Tours and Safari Operators in Zimbabwe (2015) has reported a high employee turnover in the Tourism Industry. This is a serious problem since it is very difficult to replace key skills in this sector due to high costs involved in recruitment and selection as well as training and development. The tourism Industry has been losing critical skills such as Professional Guides and Hunters to competitors in the region such as Botswana, South Africa and Namibia. The jobs in the tourism and hospitality industry are generally regarded as inferior in comparison to jobs in the other sectors. Employees in the tourism sector have very low salaries and they work long hours under poor working conditions. For example, the National Employment Council for the Tourism Industry in 2013 reported that the tourism industry was the second lowest paid sector from Agriculture despite being the highest foreign currency earner and the statistics from Collective Bargaining Agreements negotiated by the National Employment

Council for the Tourism Industry (S.I 124 of 2013, S.I 146 of 2013, S.I 118 of 2014 and S.I 122 of 2015) show that the lowest paid employee in the Tourism sector earns \$105-00 which is far below regional competitors such as Zambia, Namibia, South Africa and Botswana.

The Zimbabwe Tourism Authority reported that shortage of critical skills has impacted negatively on the performance, productivity and profitability of the Tourism Sector (Zimbabwe Tourism Bulletin 2011 and 2010), this view was also cited by the Employers' Confederation of Zimbabwe that skills flight had seen companies incurring costs in recruitment and training of new employees hence compromised productivity (E.M.C.OZ. Bulletin, 2011). Zimbabwe Parks and Wildlife Management Authority, a key player in the Tourism Sector of Zimbabwe has reported that it was seriously understaffed such that it was difficult to curb poaching using its resources and therefore it eventually appealed to the government to provide military intervention in 2015.

Given the growth prospects related to tourism in Zimbabwe and the benefits that the economy is deriving from tourism, it is critical that the industry retains critical employees irrespective of any other subsector of the industry. Therefore the current study seeks to identify the main factors that influence employee turnover intentions in the Zimbabwean Tourism industry. The rest of the paper is as follows; section 2 reviews the related literature, while section 3 presents the methodology. Section 4 summarizes the estimation results and section 5 concludes the paper.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous research in the area of employee turnover intention has shown that employees quit their jobs for a variety of reasons and these can be classified into the following: Demographic factors, Personal factors, Pull and Push factors and these will be the main centre of discussion.

Demographic Factors

Several studies focused on demographic factors such as age, gender and marital status as major determinants of employee turnover. Cohen (1993) reported that young employees had higher organizational commitment and thus low turnover intentions. This was explained in terms of the fact that young employees generally have weaker job experiences than their older counterparts and therefore have fewer alternatives in terms of changing their jobs. Luthans, Baack, and Taylor (1987) reported that gender significantly influenced employee turnover intention. According to the results of this research, male employees were found to have more organizational commitment since they generally work at better positions than the female employees. In China, Chen and Francesco (2000) found that female employees' organizational commitment was lower than that of male employees and in turn, female employee turnover intentions were higher than those of male employees. Regarding marital status, Pinar *et al.*, (2011) found that married employees had lower turnover intentions than the unmarried employees.

Personal Factors

Personal factors such as religious beliefs, family, health and dislike of the organisation have been considered to contribute to turnover intentions. Several studies have suggested that there is a relationship between personal factors and turnover intention (Chen *et al* 2014). Mustapha *et al* (2010) in their studies on 240 single mothers in Malaysia, found personal factors to work as antecedent variables. Masahudu (2008) identified employer's geographic location as a determinant of turnover intention. O'Leary and Deegan (2005) reported that employees left their jobs mainly because of the incompatibility of work and family life and that the incompatibility hampered their career advancement. For a study of employees working in a hotel, Stalcup and Pearson (2001) reported that long working hours and regular relocations were important reasons for employee turnover intentions. Other variables that influence employee turnover include heavy workloads and work stress (Ramrup & Pacis, 2008). Another important personal factor which influences employee turnover intentions is religion. A study by Lapotin (2016) reported that dozens of Muslim employees at a Wisconsin manufacturing company left their jobs after the company changed its prayer-on-the-job policy to one that prevents them from participating in their daily prayers.

2.4 Pull Factors/ Uncontrollable Factors

Past studies have suggested that there is a relationship between pull factors and intention to quit a job. Simply put, pull factors are attributes that attract someone to leave a certain place in favour of another place. These are usually called uncontrolled factors as there are out of control of the organisations though companies can use the knowledge of these to offer competitive incentives. The main pull factors have been suggested in the literature are better conditions of service such as health and safety of employees, better wages and salaries, job security, employee involvement in decision making, employee capacity building initiatives such as training and development and the reputation of the organisation.

Several studies based on western research (e.g. Boxall *et al.*, 2003; Iverson & Buttigieg, 1999; Malhotra *et al.*, 2007; Meyer & Allen, 1991; Meyer & Smith, 2000; Mowday *et al.*, 1982; Mueller & Price, 1990), have found a relationship between pull factors and employee turnover. Griffeth *et al.* (2000) have concluded from their studies that when high performers receive inadequate remuneration, they are likely to seek for alternative employment.

Furthermore, satisfaction with a job leads to high organizational commitment and thus preventing an employee from wanting to leave for uncertain future organisation (Awang & Ahmad, 2010). Ahuja *et al.* (2001) argued that an employee who does not feel satisfied with the job is likely to blame the organization leading to a lower level of commitment to the organisation. Several recent researchers (e.g. Falkenburg & Scyns, 2007; Summer & Niederman 2004; Rajendran & Chandramohan, 2010) have upheld the traditional hypotheses that high levels of job satisfaction significantly reduce employee turnover.

Push Factors/ Controlled Factors

Prior literature on turnover intentions among employees in the Tourism Industry has found out that there is a significant relationship between push factors and turnover intention. Push factors are internal to the organisation and these are aspects that compel people to leave an organisation. The push factors that have been identified in the literature are low salary, bad relationship with a boss, lack of recognition of work, unfair treatment, bad relationship with other employees, demanding work and the work environment.

Eatough (2010), argued that the main causes of interpersonal conflict with superiors are work-related behaviour and situations such as management style, resource availability, incorrect job instruction and fairness. Kropp (2013) argued that respect is something that employees are now expecting in the new and increasingly comfortable workplace. Similarly, Samantrai (1992) pointed out that a poor relationship with an immediate superior leads to employee turnover. These suggestions were confirmed by Harris, Wheeler & Kacmar, (2009), who found that a poor relationship with superiors increases turnover rates.

Poor compensation is widely acknowledged as one of the down sides in the Tourism industry (Brien, 2004; Getz, 1994; Richardson, 2008). Some past studies have shown that incentives in the form of money can be effectively used by management to attract and motivate employees to achieve organizational goals (Milkovich & Newman, 2002). Loquercio (2006) observed that it is relatively rare for people to leave well paid jobs. Although Moncraz, Zhao, and Kay (2009) stated that compensation was not the top reason for turnover among lodging properties in U.S., Chan and Kuok (2011) found a different scenario in Macau. In their research they interviewed the staffing manager of hospitality firms in Macau, and most respondents reported that inferior compensation packages were the major reason of turnover. Employees left the company for a better offer from competitors. Almost one-third of the respondents in Vong's (2003) study reported that they would change their job for a 10% increment in salary.

Career development is another factor that makes hospitality work an inferior choice of careers (Richardson, 2008). Richardson (2008) highlighted that poor or unclear career structure plagues the image of hospitality work. Thus, Hartman and Yrle (1996) investigated whether the lack of self development contributes to the turnover rate and proposed that employees are likely to quit whenever they perceive limited promotional

opportunities. Similarly, Woods, Sciarini, and Heck (1998) surveyed almost 5,000 hotel general managers and concluded that a lack of advancement opportunity is one of the most cited turnover causes.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study population

The target population for this study was all employees working in the tourism industry namely; employees in 3 star Hotels, Safaris lodges, Lodges (Leisure) and Travel Tour Operators in Zimbabwe. The study targeted managerial employees and professions such as Guides, Head Chefs, Food and Beverages Managers, Accountants and Travel and Tour Consultants. These professionals were chosen mainly because they have critical and unique skills in the tourism sector. The sample was selected as follows; first, Zimbabwe's top 5 destinations were selected (i.e. Victoria Falls, Nyanga, Kariba, Harare and Hwange), then employees were randomly selected from employees in 3 star Hotels, Safaris lodges, Lodges (Leisure) and Travel Tour Operators. A sample of 120 employees was selected

Questionnaire

Following Shah et al (2010), a survey research design was used to address the objective of this study, using a questionnaire as a data collection instrument. The questionnaire had 5 sections. The first section had questions which were used to collect the following socio- demographic factors; gender, marital status, level of education, number of children, work experience and position., The second part of the questionnaire had questions which were used to construct the following personal factors; religion, qualification, family, school availability, long working hours, complexity of job, lack of interest in organization, health and fun. The third part of the questionnaire was used to construct the pull factors and these factors were, better salary, better position, better job security, involvement in decision making, better condition of service, opportunities for employee training and organizational reputation. The push factors were constructed from questions in part four of the questionnaire. The push factors considered in this study were poor salary, bad relationship with boss, lack of recognition, lack of career advancement opportunities, unfair treatment, bad relationship with fellow employees, demanding work and poor working environment. The fifth section had 3 items that were used to construct the dependent variable used in this study (i.e the turnover intentions). One question "I often think about quitting my job" was adopted from Nyamubarwa (2013) and the other 2 questions; "as soon as I find a better job I will quit" and "I am actively searching for a new job" were adopted from Shah et al (2010). The response to each question in parts 2 to 5 was measured by a 1-5 Likert Scale with a rating of 1 indicating "Strongly Disagree" and a rating of 5 indicating "Strongly Agree."

Data Analysis Regression analysis was used to address the main objective of this study. An interval variable was constructed as an outcome variable for "intention to quit" and ranged from 1 to 15. The independent variables were socio-demographic, personal, pull and push factors. An index for personal factors was constructed from the 9 items, and this index variable ranged from 9 to 45. A second index for pull factors was also constructed from the 7 items and ranged from 7 to 35. Finally an index for the push factors was constructed from the 8 items.

4 - RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Factors

Data was collected from managerial and non managerial employees of different professions. These include; Guides, Head Chefs, Food and Beverages managers, Accountants and Travel and Tour consultants and 120 questionnaires were distributed to the participants. However, 70 usable questionnaires were returned (i.e. response rate of 58%). The distribution of the socio-demographic factors is shown in Table 1 below. The results show that most (41%) of the respondents were in the 31-40 age group. However, the majority (77%) of the participants were males. Similarly, the majority (84%) of the participants were married.

Table 1: Socio-demographic factors

Variable	Number of respondents	Frequency (%)
Age		
18-30	10	14
31-40	29	41
41-50	19	27
Above 50	12	17
Gender		
Male	54	77
Female	16	23
Marital Status		
Single	7	10
Married	59	84
Divorced	2	3
Widowed	2	3
Education		
Below O Level	14	20
O' Level	4	6
A' Level	4	6
Diploma	22	31
Degree	17	24
Masters and above	9	13
Children		
No children	10	14
1 to 3	34	49
4 to 6	17	24
7 and above	9	13
Work Experience		
1 to 3	12	13
4 to 7	21	31
8 to 10	8	12
11 and above	29	43
Position (or Salary Grade)		
Grade 1- 4	16	23
Grade 5-8	9	13
Grade 9-12	11	16
Supervisor/ General	10	13
Manager	24	35

In terms of the level of education, most of the participants (31%), had diplomas and most of them (49) had 1-3 children. In terms of work experience, most of the participants (43%) had at least 11 years experience and only a small proportion (12%) had 8-10 years of work experiences.

Descriptive statistics

The results in Table 2 below indicate that about 33% of the respondents were actively looking for new jobs and 39 % were contemplating on quitting their jobs.

Table 2: Intention to quit from current job

Questions	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
1. I often think about quitting my job.	7.58	31.82	22.73	25.76	12.12
2. As soon as I find a better job I will quit.	3.03	9.09	10.61	34.85	42.42
3. I am actively searching for a new job.	9.09	24.24	10.61	33.33	22.73

Regression results

In order to determine whether socio-demographic, personal, pull and push factors significantly explain employee turnover intentions in the Zimbabwean tourism sector, a regression model was estimated. A general regression model was first estimated and then all the statistically insignificant variables were deleted in order to come up with a more parsimonious model. The results of the specific model are presented in table 3 below. These results suggest that socio-demographic factors such as age, marital status, number of children, work experience and employee's salary grade do not significantly influence the turnover intentions of employees in the Zimbabwean tourism sector. In addition, personal factors (e.g. religious beliefs, jobs below employee's qualifications, transferred to an area with no good schools) do not significantly influence employee turnover intentions. These results contract previous studies that have found such factors to be important in explaining employee turnover intentions (e.g. Cohen, 1993; Masahudu, 2008 and Punar *et al*, 2011).

Table 3: Factors influencing intention to quit

Variable	Coefficient	Std. error	p-value
Constant	-3.558	0.805	0.235
Gender	2.463*	0.234	0.003
Education	-0.399***	0.091	0.093
Push	0.266***	0.089	0.005
Pull	0.257***	2.966	0.005

However, the results indicate that the coefficient on gender is positive and significantly different from zero at the 1% level of significance. Thus, male employees in the Zimbabwean tourism sector have a higher turnover intention rate than their female counterparts. This is in contrast to the findings of, Chen and Francesco (2000) who found that female employee turnover intentions were higher than those of male

employees. The level of education variable was found to be significant at the 10% level, which implies that highly educated employees have a lower turnover intention rate than the less educated employees.

The other important determinant of employee turnover was the composite push factor. The coefficient on this factor was positive and significant and thus indicating that push factors like low salary, bad relationships with fellow employees, lack of recognition at work, no career advancement, not treated fairly and bad working environment can significantly increase the employee turnover intentions in the Zimbabwean tourism sector.

Finally, the positive and significant influence of the composite pull factor implies that existence of other organisations offering better salaries, conditions of service and job securities increases the employee turnover rate.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The major finding of this study is that gender, education, push and pulls factors significantly influence turnover intentions of employees in tourism sector in Zimbabwe. Thus, despite the high unemployment rate currently prevailing in Zimbabwe, the results of this study are still in line with previous research. Therefore human resource managers may reduce employee turnover rates in their respective organizations by paying more attention to push and pull factors

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